

COPING WITH EMOTIONS: A STATUS OF STUDENTS INITIATING POST-GRADUATION STUDY

Dr. Vijay Sansare

Assistant Professor, BPHES' CSRD - Institute of Social Work and Research, Ahilyanagar

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Abstract

The human life span is surrounded by emotions. Emotions play an important role in each one's life. Emotions direct feeling, thinking, behaviour or action. Emotions may be visible or invisible by nature and may be noted by oneself or near and dear ones. A person passing from one stage to another discovers a number of emotions. The individual grows as he gets several experiences and exposure, and gets involved in various events and activities in life. The number of different activities and experiences leads to developing coping with overwhelming emotions. As individuals transition into youth and adulthood, a number of aspects of the inner self mature and stabilise.

The present paper highlights the status of coping abilities of post-graduate social work students. These students have experiences of around twenty-two years. This was inclusive of the family life, schooling, peer life and different clubs or groups as a social life. Most of life is experienced in schooling and higher education, which helps to understand oneself and develop more maturity. The individual experiences positive and negative emotions in this period of life. The paper throws light on learning types of emotions, patterns of emotional behaviour and most importantly, the ways of tackling emotions. The emotions guide behaviour and action. Experiencing emotion in a natural but coping with emotions sometimes becomes challenging. Simply, the article displays the scaled emotions amongst growing youth. These youth were just in the imitation process of social work studies in post-graduation.

Key Words: *Emotions, types of emotions, emotional behaviour, tackling ways with emotions.*

Introduction :

Post-graduate (P.G.) students enter higher education to pursue a specific career in life. This period of their life is crucial for the individual and their near and dear ones. It is a perfect time to take responsibility for themselves. The maturity level of students is considered to be the best. It is an age of turning points for young lives. This stage leads them to ground themselves and prepare for future ventures. Therefore, for about 21 years, life experiences with family, peers,

schooling and social life help them to understand their emotions and behaviour they show while being emotional. They experience several incidents and events in their personal and social life, which make them realise the condition of their emotions. The person learns to express the emotion from childhood, but fails underhand types of emotion. As a child grows into adolescence or the age of storm, they have several emotions intently expressing and learn to discover more and more emotions. However, towards the end of adolescent age and the entry point of youth life, a person is found to be understanding emotions and having more control than before. Thereafter, emotions stabilise as individuals experience a number of roles and responsibilities.

Woolworth (1945) defines “Emotion is a ‘Moved or stirred up ’state of an organism that appears as feelings to the individual himself and as disturbed muscular and glandular activities to an external observer”. This definition indicates emotions are expressed when a person feels provoked or excited mentally from within. The individual experiences through feelings such as anger, happiness or fear. It also shows changes or movement externally through body language or physical action reactions. William McDougall (1949) says, “An instinct is an inherited or innate psycho-physical disposition which determines its possessor to perceive and to pay attention to, objects of a certain class, to experience an emotional excitement of a particular quality upon perceiving such an object, and to act regarding it in a particular manner, or, at least, to experience an impulse to such an action”. In this definition the instinct or drives that lead to emotional behaviour are observed, and it is the production of perception. Each emotional reaction, experience, or response involves instincts to make some action.

“Emotion is a complex chain of loosely connected events that begins with stills and includes feelings, psychological changes, impulses to action, and specific goal-directed behaviour”, said Plutchik R. (2001). As noted, emotion is not a single response or action but rather a series of interconnected processes. Emotional response is ignited with stimuli to create an inner feeling. It depicts physiological changes that lead to action or show action in a certain way, which is goal-oriented. He had also noted eight basic emotions, including joy, trust, fear, surprise, sadness, disgust, anger and anticipation, a mixture of positive and negative emotions of life.

Ultimately, the above definition helps to understand that emotions are felt internally and expressed through behaviour and action. Emotions are feelings as noted through experiences such as anger, happiness or fear. It was also learnt that emotions are instincts or inborn drives. The instincts become a guide for the individual to perceive, feel and respond to a particular

situation or context. It sheds light on instincts that prompt emotional responses. It also talks about feelings and psychological and physiological changes an individual experiences.

At the P.G. level, students are persons who have completed an undergraduate degree and enter into the master's degree, the highest vital degree in the Indian education system, preparing and making them employable with knowledge, skills and attitudes. Looking at the above definitions, students are experiencing such feelings and continue to express their emotions in life survival and adjustment. The emotions are visible through their behaviour patterns. Students step up to get advanced with most professional skills and employable skills while continuing higher studies by balancing their emotions at every stage. However, at the same time, these students experience emotional life in education, affection, recreation and in achievement, crisis and failures too. Youth at this level become emotional because of education, roles, responsibilities, needs, requirements, and others' expectations.

Ultimately, it is learnt that emotions are an inner arousal due to instincts or events that make an individual behave in a certain way. Pleasant and unpleasant emotions are portrayed by a person, which may lead to harm or feel better. A person at a young age is just calming the emotion and learning to express appropriately or control it to some or a greater extent. The paper aims to learn how a person completing an undergraduate degree, having life's good and bad experiences of over 21 and more in some cases years and has crossed the adolescents age had coping ability with emotions. It is derived from the above definitions and is viewed that emotion can be with five components, namely: affective, cognitive, physiological, motivational and expressive by nature. It can be concluded that emotion is observed in every living organism.

PG students look at themselves, their family and their future struggles and decide to step into a particular profession. The students growing with maturity turn out to be serious about future careers. The Master of Social Work (MSW) is a theoretical as well as a fieldwork study. The students taking admission and after getting enrollment understand emotions better and also tackle them accordingly. Students staying at college or an institute campus make them more emotional, being away from family, friends, location and continue to experience emotional behaviours thereafter. This emotionality is not only about the present situation but also matters about past life incidents and future concerns and endeavours.

Over time, they learn various aspects of their emotions. They have also developed several coping mechanisms for emotions. The growing maturity and developing understanding lead to coping with emotions. Emotions are affected by various factors in life that come into our lives.

At times, a person may have pleasant and unpleasant emotions in their day-to-day life. Getting emotional is a natural phenomenon and universal in nature. Emotions are very much personal; therefore, a person's emotional intensity may vary from person to person. The motions matter in feeling, behaviour, treating, talking, resolutions, successes and moreover with academic performances in the present study context.

Brief Literature Review:

Pekrun et al. (2002) give an account of influences on students' learning and achievement of the academic emotions. It stresses a wide range of positive and negative emotions amongst the students in an academic environment. The Academic Emotions Questionnaire was introduced by an author as a reliable tool to learn about emotional experiences. The key finding understood was that emotions make a significant difference in motivation, cognitive life and self-regulated learning. It was also explained how the perception of control and value shares emotional responses. It threw light on learning about incorporating emotional aspects in education and the need to understand emotional processes.

Reschly et al. (2008) used Fredrickson's Broaden-and-Build Theory to learn the role of positive emotions and enhance adolescents' engagement and performance in school. It was noted that positive emotions had a higher engagement in school, while negative emotions were linked to lower engagement. It was all brought out in various adaptive coping strategies for improving school engagement with positive emotions. The study highlighted the significance of encouraging positive emotions for well-being and improving academic involvement.

Tomas et al. (2016) highlighted the importance of emotion regulation in enhancing engagement and learning in a classroom setting. The study involved a group task based on a video-based socio-scientific task. This made participants experience the positive and negative emotions. It was found that actively regulated negative emotions helped them to achieve academic goals profoundly, along with maintaining appropriate peer relationships.

Li et al. (2020) presented a neuroscience-based perspective on positive emotions. The education was a main concern to understand the impact on attention, memory and motivation for improving performance for learning. It was also noted that positive emotions develop the cognitive processes. The study throws light on fostering positive emotional climates to improve learning outcomes and student well-being through the brain mechanism. It also included the amygdala and prefrontal regions.

An article written by Raccanello et al. (2020) critically analysed the negative achievement emotions. It was centred around the ethnic minority and majority in various ways with

emotional abilities. The performance and well-being are affected by negative emotions such as anger, hopelessness, embarrassment and boredom. Findings portrayed that minority students experience higher levels of negative emotions compared to majority students, specifically in subjects like mathematics and language during their educational life. It was noted that poor emotional competence leads to heightened negative types of emotions. The study discovered the vitality of understanding disparity in educational institutions to address the concern of emotionality effectively and improve educational performance, along with having good well-being.

Deng et al. (2022) explain the influence of online learning on high school students by mediating and regulatory aspects on academic emotions. It was analysed that promotion led to a positive impact while prevention led to a negative effect. Positive academic emotions and self-efficacy had enhanced engagement in learning processes, whereas negative emotions reduced the engagement. Fostering positive motivation and emotional experiences has improved learning among students online.

Nguyen and Janssens (2025) found that emotions are a performative indicator to shape morally tense relations. It was illustrated about the reinforcement of emotions in power imbalances and marginalisation. It was also confirmed that emotions play a critical role in constituting ethical relations sustaining in future. Chen (2025) analysed the influences of academic emotions on relational concerns using the Control-Value Theory framework of secondary students. It was stressed that negative emotions were significantly reduced directly. The cultural context was highlighted in the realisation of improving learning results and emotional elements.

The above brief review indicates the impact of positive emotions on academic performances, relational aspects and the importance of cultural content in shaping students for good citizens.

Theoretical Concern;

The Emotion-Focused Coping concept was introduced by Lazarus R. & Folkman S. (1984) under the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping, which talks about the regulation of emotional responses to stressors in life. The theory refers to strategies to manage emotional distress. It learnt seeking emotional support, acceptance, positivity, avoidance and relaxation techniques to manage emotional life. The present paper centres on these concepts of Emotion-Focused Coping of PG students, in order to understand the status of coping with emotion. The students initiating a new study require a specific strategy to address emotional concerns of anxiety, uncertainty and emotional strain related to academic and social life. These were also found to be impacted due to Covid-19, and found engaging in social media. Therefore, the

theoretical concept made the present paper more relevant to understand the status of coping with emotions of PG students.

Aims and Methodology:

The paper aimed to understand the coping status of emotions at the time of initiating post-graduation study. The study also highlighted participants' patterns of emotional experiences. The study also tried to understand the ways to cope with emotions.

The paper is based on empirical data. The descriptive research method was used to understand the coping level of emotions among PG students of social work, including quantitative and qualitative data. The standardised scale was used to collect primary quantitative data to measure the status. The standardised tool of a five-point rating was referred to for the study. The scale had positive and negative marking statements. The sample size for scale administration was 183 post-graduation social work students. Participants were from three Maharashtra districts: Ahmednagar, Nasik and Pune. Findings were drawn based on scaled data. The observations of participants were another vital qualitative data that were used for the inferences. The primary data is part of a PhD study on coping with the emotion variable. The data was collected immediately after enrollment in the social work post-graduate degree. The paper itself is empirical by nature. The primary data collected was found trustworthy, as the maturity level of the students was considered more stable and confident at this stage of life.

Profile of Participants:

A total of 183 students were studying at a college and two institutions of social work. Total 44.8% participants were from CSRD - Institute of Social Work and Research, Ahilyanagar (Ahmednagar), while 25.13% from College of Social Work, Nasik and 30.05% from Karve Institute of Social Service, Pune. A college and institutions are affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune.

The newly enrolled participants for the PG social work course were considered in this study with appropriate consent.

Status of Coping with Emotions:

■ ISWR ■ CSW ■ KINSS

The following table shows the primary quantitative data of participants. It indicates the coping status with emotions by research participants with a five-point rating scale.

The above chart indicates the entry-level status of coping with emotions of P.G. social work students enrolled in a college and two institutions. The classification of coping with emotion at an entry as a very high level was 5.50%, whereas 19.70% was at a high level, 62.80% at an average level, a low level was 8.70%, and a very low level was 3.30%. The table indicated that most participants were scaled highest at an average for coping with emotions.

Qualitative Analysis:

The present analysis was based on observations and initial interactions with students individually and in small groups. The participants at this stage with emotional status showed complex concerns. It was noted that participants indicated several emotions, such as hope, anxiety, stress and motivation. One could understand that emotional aspects are associated with perception and opportunities due to the migration and transition phase. Participants were also found to utilise the concept of emotion-focused coping in their personal lives. The positive emotions were considered as a better strategy to cope with emotions by being optimistic and having a purpose for life in future for better survival. It made the participant more resilient and psychologically sound for adjustment in the transition phase. The negative emotions were also observed impacting the lives of participants. Negative emotions such as fear, loneliness, and sadness impact appropriate decision-making and well-being at this kind of stage. One of the vital aspects was that family members, peers or friends played a crucial role in regulating the emotional experiences of participants, as they had provided emotional and social support to a great extent, as observed. It was also learnt that emotional awareness and coping mechanisms are essential for maintaining mental health and adapting to new life roles in new settings.

Participants found coping with emotions through silence and avoidance more at this juncture of the phase. Participants practice being positive in thought, mindfulness, relaxing, and engaging with co-friends and entertainment, which is considered for addressing emotional aspects. Denial, non-acceptance, silence, and shyness avoidance were some aspects noted as maladaptive practices at the time of experiencing emotions.

Discussions;

Emotions are an integral part of life. It influences the thought, behaviour and action of individuals in various walks of life. A person develops gradually to cope with emotions through life experiences, social life and education. PG students experience a wide range of emotions at this kind of phase of life. Positive and negative emotions are shaped by experiences, present challenges and future aspirations or ambitions over time. With increasing age, experiences, interactions and education enhance maturity and understanding of the impacts on coping with emotions. The expression of emotions varies from individual to individual due to grasping and understanding ability, relating and thinking capacity. Emotional awareness and coping abilities are highly needed for a person. It also seeks academic improvement, personal and professional development for holistic wellbeing.

A brief review depicts that learning, motivations, cognitive development and performance are influenced significantly by positive and negative emotions. Engagement, self-regulated learning and well-being get enhanced with positive emotions. However, negative emotions become a barrier to achievement and life development. It was also noted that emotional competence and regulation are vital in managing and improving performance by updating positive coping strategies with emotions. Cultural, social and learning environment context regulates the outcomes and emotional experiences of a life. The review highlights the significance of promoting positive emotional climates and coping abilities for holistic wellbeing.

The study was grounded in Emotional-Focused Coping. The element was drawn from a Transactional Model of Stress and Coping. It regulates emotional distress during the academic transition for students in higher education in the context of the present study. The students identify coping strategies for emotions to overcome and have a more productive life. The descriptive study with an empirical nature stressed the quantitative coping level and qualitative strategies for coping with emotional patterns. The coping mechanism is found to ensure emotional stability and adjustment among PG students.

Quantitative findings brought out that the majority (62.80%) of research participants fall under the category of average level coping with emotions. It is a moderate level of emotional adjustment at this point, and is also the result of a reduction in social and educational contact due to the Covid-19 pandemic in their life. Participants also found that exhibiting mixed emotions to note some hope, anxiety, stress and motivation shaping its complexity with transition and migration exposure. The participants mostly found themselves relying on self-focused emotional strategies in their lives, such as adapting positive behaviour and seeking support from peers.

Interestingly, all the newly enrolled P.G. students are highly needed to build their ability or competencies to cope with emotions with several strategies. The proper advice, guidance, and consulting with the appropriate person will contribute to coping with emotions by including entertainment, sports, yoga and meditation, and getting engaged in hobbies. The participants can also undergo life skills training to face emotions effectively in their lives.

Conclusions

The study reaffirms that individuals' cognition, behaviour and actions are significantly influenced in the transition phase of higher education. PG students experience a complex interplay of positive and negative emotions. These emotions are shaped by past, present, and specifically future aspirations at this age. Literature threw light on positive emotions that enhance the learning, motivations and well-being of individuals, while negative becomes a hindering factor to improve performances and development. The study was grounded in Emotion-Focused Coping, where an individual finds ways to deal with such kind of feelings and emotions. The participants demonstrated an average level of coping with emotions, which was also impacted by the pandemic, and need to improve on a significant or drastic level for a healthy life and well-being. Relying predominantly on adaptive coping mechanisms indicates the need to learn various other strategies to deal with emotional expression more effectively by training in life skills, counselling, seeking guidance and exposing oneself to life experiences for strengthening emotional ability to cope with emotions. The continuous starving behaviour to cope with emotions will have a significant impact on the lives of such kind of participants.

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